

Supplementary material

Tables

Table S1. STROBE Statement—Checklist of items that should be included in reports of cross-sectional studies, with location in the manuscript.

Item	No	Recommendation	Reported in section
<i>Title and abstract</i>			
Title and abstract	1	(a) Indicate the study's design with a commonly used term in the title or the abstract	Title; Abstract, METHODS
		(b) Provide in the abstract an informative and balanced summary of what was done and what was found	Abstract
<i>Introduction</i>			
Background/rationale	2	Explain the scientific background and rationale for the investigation being reported	Introduction, paragraphs 1–4
Objectives	3	State specific objectives, including any prespecified hypotheses	Introduction, paragraph 5
<i>Methods</i>			
Study design	4	Present key elements of study design early in the paper	Methods, Study design and data source
Setting	5	Describe the setting, locations, and relevant dates, including periods of recruitment, exposure, follow-up, and data collection	Methods, Study design and data source
Participants	6	(a) Give the eligibility criteria, and the sources and methods of selection of participants	Methods, Study population

Variables	7	Clearly define all outcomes, exposures, predictors, potential confounders, and effect modifiers. Give diagnostic criteria, if applicable	Methods, Outcome variable; Methods, Covariates; Table S2
Data sources/measurement	8	For each variable of interest, give sources of data and details of methods of assessment (measurement). Describe comparability of assessment methods if there is more than one group	Methods, Outcome variable; Methods, Covariates; Table S2
Bias	9	Describe any efforts to address potential sources of bias	Methods, Statistical analysis (survey weights, multicollinearity); Discussion, Limitations
Study size	10	Explain how the study size was arrived at	Methods, Study population (n = 29,889 after exclusion of missing data)
Quantitative variables	11	Explain how quantitative variables were handled in the analyses. If applicable, describe which groupings were chosen and why	Methods, Covariates (age groups, wealth quintiles, media categories); Methods, Statistical analysis
Statistical methods	12	(a) Describe all statistical methods, including those used to control for confounding	Methods, Statistical analysis (multilevel modelling)
		(b) Describe any methods used to examine subgroups and interactions	Methods, Sensitivity and exploratory analyses (interaction analysis, LCA)
		(c) Explain how missing data were addressed	Methods, Study population (records with missing outcome excluded)
		(d) If applicable, describe analytical methods taking account of sampling strategy	Methods, Statistical analysis (Carle's scaling method; survey-weighted prevalence)

(e) Describe any sensitivity analyses

Methods, Sensitivity and exploratory analyses

Results

Participants

13 (a) Report numbers of individuals at each stage of study—e.g., numbers potentially eligible, examined for eligibility, confirmed eligible, included in the study, completing follow-up, and analysed

Results, paragraph 1 (n = 29,889)

(b) Give reasons for non-participation at each stage

Methods, Study population (exclusion of missing data on primary outcome)

(c) Consider use of a flow diagram

Not applicable (secondary analysis of existing survey data)

Descriptive data

14 (a) Give characteristics of study participants (e.g., demographic, clinical, social) and information on exposures and potential confounders

Results, paragraph 1; Table 1

(b) Indicate number of participants with missing data for each variable of interest

Methods, Study population (complete-case analysis after exclusion)

Outcome data

15 Report numbers of outcome events or summary measures

Results, paragraph 2 (27.5%); Table 2

Main results

16 (a) Give unadjusted estimates and, if applicable, confounder-adjusted estimates and their precision (e.g., 95% confidence interval). Make clear which confounders were adjusted for and why they were included

Results, paragraphs 3–4; Figure 2; Table S6

(b) Report category boundaries when continuous variables were categorised

Methods, Covariates (age groups, altitude per 1,000 m)

	(c) If relevant, consider translating estimates of relative risk into absolute risk for a meaningful time period	Not applicable (cross-sectional prevalence study)
Other analyses	17 Report other analyses done—e.g., analyses of subgroups and interactions, and sensitivity analyses	Results, paragraphs 5–6; Tables S7–S13; Figures S3–S5
Discussion		
Key results	18 Summarise key results with reference to study objectives	Discussion, paragraphs 1–2
Limitations	19 Discuss limitations of the study, taking into account sources of potential bias or imprecision. Discuss both direction and magnitude of any potential bias	Discussion, Limitations paragraph
Interpretation	20 Give a cautious overall interpretation of results considering objectives, limitations, multiplicity of analyses, results from similar studies, and other relevant evidence	Discussion, paragraphs 3–7
Generalisability	21 Discuss the generalisability (external validity) of the study results	Discussion, Limitations paragraph (last sentence)
Other information		
Funding	22 Give the source of funding and the role of the funders for the present study and, if applicable, for the original study on which the present article is based	Acknowledgements, Funding sources

Reference: von Elm E, et al. STROBE Initiative. Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology (STROBE) statement: guidelines for reporting observational studies. *PLoS Med.* 2007;4(10):e296.

LCA: Latent Class Analysis.

Table S2. Operational definitions of study variables, Peru Demographic and Health Survey (ENDES) 2024.

Variable	Definition	Source
<i>Outcome variables</i>		
Comprehensive TB knowledge	Knows TB is airborne (v474a = 1) + rejects $\geq 3/5$ myths (v474b–f) + knows TB is curable (v475 = 1) + non-stigmatising attitude (v476 = 0)	Constructed
Correct transmission knowledge	Knows TB spreads through air (v474a = 1)	ENDES v474a
TB curability knowledge	Knows TB can be cured (v475 = 1)	ENDES v475
Non-stigmatising attitude	Would not keep secret if family member had TB (v476 = 0)	ENDES v476
<i>Individual-level covariates</i>		
Age group	Categorised from continuous age (v012): 15–24, 25–34, 35–44, 45–49 years	ENDES v012
Education level	Highest level attended: None, Primary, Secondary, Higher	ENDES v106
Media exposure	Additive score from three binary indicators: reads newspaper/magazine (v157 > 0), listens to radio (v158 > 0), watches television (v159 > 0). Categorised as: no media (score = 0), 1 source (score = 1), 2–3 sources (score ≥ 2)	ENDES v157, v158, v159

***Household-level
covariates***

Wealth index	DHS wealth index quintiles: Poorest (Q1), Poorer (Q2), Middle (Q3), Richer (Q4), Richest (Q5)	ENDES v190
Improved water source	Binary: improved (piped water, borehole, protected well, bottled water; v113 codes 11–14, 21) vs. not improved	ENDES v113
Improved sanitation	Binary: improved (flush toilet, ventilated improved pit latrine; v116 codes 11–13, 21–22) vs. not improved	ENDES v116

***Contextual-level
covariates
(cluster/department)***

Area of residence	Urban vs. Rural	ENDES v025
Altitude	Cluster altitude in metres above sea level, rescaled per 1,000 m (v040/1,000)	ENDES v040
Natural region	Coast, Highlands, Jungle (INEI official classification)	ENDES v024
Departmental TB incidence rate	Reported TB cases per 100,000 population, rescaled per 100 cases (rate/100)	MINSA/INEI 2021
Cluster coordinates	Latitude and longitude from district centroid (ubigeo package)	Ubigeo

***Extension variables
(exploratory analyses)***

Health care access barriers score	Sum of nine binary items (v467a–i), each coded 1 = “gran problema” (great problem), 0 = not a problem. Items: knowing where to go (a), getting permission (b), getting money for treatment (c), distance to facility (d), getting transport (e), not wanting to go alone (f), concern about female staff (g), concern about available staff (h), concern about available medicines (i). Range: 0–9	ENDES v467a–v467i
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TB: tuberculosis; DHS: Demographic and Health Survey; ENDES: Encuesta Demográfica y de Salud Familiar; MINSA: Ministerio de Salud; INEI: Instituto Nacional de Estadística e Informática. Variables are organised by analytical level.

Table S3. Generalised variance inflation factors (GVIF) for the fully adjusted multilevel model (M4).

Variable	GVIF	Df	GVIF^(1/2Df)	Status
Age group	1.15	3	1.02	OK
Education level	1.37	3	1.05	OK
Media exposure	1.03	2	1.01	OK
Wealth index	1.86	4	1.08	OK
Improved water source	1.16	1	1.08	OK
Improved sanitation	1.37	1	1.17	OK
Area of residence	1.53	1	1.23	OK
Altitude (scaled)	1.60	1	1.27	OK
Region	1.97	2	1.18	OK
Departmental TB incidence rate	1.50	1	1.22	OK

GVIF: generalised variance inflation factor; DF: degrees of freedom.

Table S4. Model comparison M0–M5.

Model	AIC	BIC	Log Lik	R² marginal	R² conditional	ICC
M0	27563	27588	-13779	0.000	0.222	0.222
M1	26723	26814	-13350	0.063	0.262	0.213
M2	26702	26843	-13334	0.070	0.267	0.212
M3	26684	26842	-13323	0.076	0.272	0.212
M4	26675	26858	-13316	0.078	0.267	0.205
M5	26677	26851	-13317	0.073	0.265	0.207

AIC: Akaike Information Criterion; BIC: Bayesian Information Criterion; ICC: Intraclass Correlation Coefficient.

Table S5. Verification of multilevel logistic regression assumptions for the fully adjusted model (M4).

Assumption	Verification method	Result	Conclusion
Linearity in the logit	GAM with splines	Approximately linear relationships	Met
Absence of multicollinearity	Generalized VIF	VIF max = 1.27 < 5	Met (no multicollinearity)
Normality of random effects (department)	Shapiro-Wilk test	W = 0.965, P = 0.526	Not significant; normality assumption met
Homogeneity of variance	Residuals vs fitted	No systematic pattern (see Figure S12)	Met
Absence of overdispersion	Dispersion parameter	phi = 0.826 ~ 1	Met

GAM: generalised additive model; VIF: variance inflation factor.

Table S6. Consolidated fixed effects, random effects, and model fit across sequential multilevel models (M0-M5).

Variable	M0 OR (95% CI)	M0 p-value	M1 OR (95% CI)	M1 p-value	M2 OR (95% CI)	M2 p-value	M3 OR (95% CI)	M3 p-value	M4 OR (95% CI)	M4 p-value	M5 OR (95% CI)	M5 p-value
(Intercept)	0.26 (0.23-0.28)	<0.001	0.04 (0.03-0.06)	<0.001	0.04 (0.02-0.05)	<0.001	0.04 (0.02-0.06)	<0.001	0.02 (0.02-0.04)	<0.001	0.03 (0.02-0.05)	<0.001
Age group												
15-24 (ref.)												
25-34			1.77 (1.63-1.93)	<0.001	1.77 (1.63-1.93)	<0.001	1.77 (1.62-1.92)	<0.001	1.76 (1.62-1.92)	<0.001	1.76 (1.62-1.92)	<0.001
35-44			2.54 (2.34-2.77)	<0.001	2.50 (2.30-2.72)	<0.001	2.50 (2.30-2.72)	<0.001	2.50 (2.30-2.72)	<0.001	2.50 (2.30-2.72)	<0.001
45-49			2.74 (2.47-3.05)	<0.001	2.68 (2.41-2.98)	<0.001	2.68 (2.40-2.98)	<0.001	2.67 (2.40-2.98)	<0.001	2.68 (2.41-2.98)	<0.001
Education level												
No education (ref.)												
Primary			1.50 (1.07-2.11)	0.020	1.49 (1.06-2.09)	0.023	1.48 (1.05-2.09)	0.024	1.48 (1.05-2.08)	0.025	1.48 (1.05-2.08)	0.025
Secondary			3.12 (2.22-4.38)	<0.001	2.99 (2.13-4.19)	<0.001	2.99 (2.13-4.20)	<0.001	2.98 (2.12-4.18)	<0.001	2.98 (2.12-4.19)	<0.001
Higher			5.13 (3.65-7.21)	<0.001	4.65 (3.30-6.56)	<0.001	4.69 (3.32-6.61)	<0.001	4.66 (3.30-6.57)	<0.001	4.67 (3.31-6.59)	<0.001
Media exposure												
No media (ref.)												
1 source			0.92 (0.78-1.09)	0.356	0.91 (0.76-1.07)	0.255	0.90 (0.76-1.07)	0.245	0.90 (0.76-1.07)	0.234	0.90 (0.76-1.07)	0.233
2-3 sources			1.01 (0.86-1.18)	0.897	0.98 (0.84-1.15)	0.822	0.98 (0.84-1.15)	0.827	0.98 (0.84-1.15)	0.809	0.98 (0.84-1.15)	0.800
Wealth index												
Poorest (ref.)												
Poorer					1.05 (0.94-1.16)	0.399	1.07 (0.96-1.20)	0.219	1.08 (0.96-1.21)	0.206	1.08 (0.96-1.21)	0.204
Middle					1.10 (0.97-1.24)	0.124	1.14 (1.00-1.30)	0.057	1.15 (1.00-1.31)	0.043	1.15 (1.00-1.31)	0.043
Richer					1.25 (1.08-1.46)	0.003	1.29 (1.10-1.52)	0.002	1.31 (1.11-1.54)	0.001	1.32 (1.12-1.55)	<0.001
Richest					1.30 (1.14-1.49)	<0.001	1.35 (1.17-1.56)	<0.001	1.37 (1.18-1.58)	<0.001	1.37 (1.18-1.59)	<0.001
Improved water source					1.24 (1.09-1.41)	<0.001	1.26 (1.11-1.44)	<0.001	1.26 (1.11-1.43)	<0.001	1.26 (1.11-1.43)	<0.001
Improved sanitation					0.99 (0.89-1.11)	0.924	1.01 (0.91-1.13)	0.816	1.02 (0.92-1.13)	0.712	1.02 (0.92-1.13)	0.727
Area of residence												

Variable	M0 OR (95% CI)	M0 p-value	M1 OR (95% CI)	M1 p-value	M2 OR (95% CI)	M2 p-value	M3 OR (95% CI)	M3 p-value	M4 OR (95% CI)	M4 p-value	M5 OR (95% CI)	M5 p-value
Urban (ref.)												
Rural							1.19 (1.04-1.35)	0.009	1.19 (1.04-1.35)	0.009	1.18 (1.04-1.35)	0.012
Altitude (scaled)							0.89 (0.85-0.94)	<0.001	0.89 (0.84-0.94)	<0.001	0.88 (0.83-0.93)	<0.001
Region												
Coast (ref.)												
Highlands									1.53 (1.20-1.97)	<0.001	1.39 (1.09-1.78)	0.009
Jungle									1.55 (1.22-1.96)	<0.001	1.58 (1.22-2.05)	<0.001
Departmental TB incidence rate									1.21 (1.01-1.44)	0.035		
Random effects												
Var(cluster)	0.8818		0.8285		0.8186		0.8117		0.8148		0.8129	
Var(department)	0.0589		0.0624		0.0673		0.0738		0.0336		0.0441	
ICC cluster (%)	20.8		19.8		19.6		19.4		19.7		19.6	
ICC department (%)	1.4		1.5		1.6		1.8		0.8		1.1	
ICC total (%)	22.2		21.3		21.2		21.2		20.5		20.7	
Model fit												
AIC	27563.2		26722.9		26702.2		26684.1		26675.0		26676.9	
BIC	27588.1		26814.2		26843.4		26841.9		26857.8		26851.3	
Log-likelihood	-13778.6		-13350.4		-13334.1		-13323.0		-13315.5		-13317.4	
R2 marginal	0.000		0.063		0.070		0.076		0.078		0.073	
R2 conditional	0.222		0.262		0.267		0.272		0.267		0.265	
Observations	29,889		29,889		29,889		29,889		29,889		29,889	

OR: odds ratio; CI: confidence interval; TB: tuberculosis; AIC: Akaike Information Criterion; BIC: Bayesian Information Criterion; ICC: intraclass correlation coefficient; R²: coefficient of determination.

Table S7. Local Indicators of Spatial Association (LISA) cluster classification of primary sampling units (n = 3,074).

LISA cluster	n	%
High-High (hotspot)	11	0.4
Low-High (outlier)	7	0.2
Not significant	3,056	99.4

LISA: Local Indicators of Spatial Association.

Table S8. Sensitivity analysis: spatial autocorrelation (Moran's I) by number of nearest neighbours (k).

k	Moran I	Z score	P value
4	0.0739	6.73	< 0.001
6	0.0780	8.55	< 0.001
8	0.0770	9.66	< 0.001
10	0.0680	9.49	< 0.001
15	0.0696	11.80	< 0.001
20	0.0654	12.81	< 0.001

Table S9. Prevalence of tuberculosis knowledge under alternative outcome definitions (n = 29,889).

Definition	N	Prevalence
Main (>=3/5 myths)	29889	27.50%
Strict (5/5 myths)	29889	14.20%
Relaxed (>=2/5 myths)	29889	27.60%
Extended (+ attitudes s489)	29771	21.30%
With symptoms (+ s481ae)	26914	2.20%

Table S10. Sensitivity analysis: adjusted odds ratios for key predictors under alternative outcome definitions and model specifications.

Variable	Main (>=3/5)	Strict (5/5)	Relaxed (>=2/5)	2 levels	Without weights
Education level: Higher	4.66 (3.30-6.57)	2.33 (1.53-3.55)	4.68 (3.32-6.61)	4.25 (3.01-6.00)	4.41 (3.08-6.31)
Wealth index: Richest	1.37 (1.18-1.58)	1.08 (0.89-1.31)	1.37 (1.19-1.59)	1.26 (1.09-1.46)	1.18 (1.04-1.34)
Area of residence: Rural	1.19 (1.04-1.35)	0.95 (0.81-1.13)	1.19 (1.04-1.35)	1.12 (0.99-1.28)	1.02 (0.93-1.12)
Region: Highlands	1.53 (1.20-1.97)	1.15 (0.79-1.69)	1.54 (1.20-1.99)	1.35 (1.15-1.58)	1.44 (1.14-1.82)
Region: Jungle	1.55 (1.22-1.96)	1.00 (0.69-1.46)	1.56 (1.23-1.99)	1.45 (1.28-1.64)	1.44 (1.14-1.83)
Departmental TB incidence rate	1.21 (1.01-1.44)	1.09 (0.82-1.44)	1.20 (1.01-1.43)	1.18 (1.10-1.28)	1.12 (0.94-1.35)

OR: odds ratio; CI: confidence interval; TB: tuberculosis.

Table S11. Comparison of multilevel model fit with and without Carle-rescaled survey weights.

Model	AIC	Singular
Model 4 with Carle weights (primary)	26,675	No
Model 4 without weights (sensitivity)	31,963	No

AIC: Akaike Information Criterion.

Table S12. Latent Class Analysis model fit comparison for 2-class to 5-class solutions.

Classes	BIC	AIC	Log Lik
2	184399.7	184291.8	-92132.9
3	184320.7	184154.6	-92057.3
4	184329.6	184105.4	-92025.7
5	184393.8	184111.4	-92021.7

LCA: Latent Class Analysis; BIC: Bayesian Information Criterion; AIC: Akaike Information Criterion, Log Lik: log-likelihood.

Table S13. Latent Class Analysis: conditional item-response probabilities for the 3-class model.

Variable	Class	Category	Probability
TB knowledge	Informed-connected	No comprehensive knowledge	0.607
TB knowledge	Informed-connected	Comprehensive knowledge	0.393
TB knowledge	Moderate-mixed	No comprehensive knowledge	0.772
TB knowledge	Moderate-mixed	Comprehensive knowledge	0.228
TB knowledge	Vulnerable-disconnected	No comprehensive knowledge	0.855
TB knowledge	Vulnerable-disconnected	Comprehensive knowledge	0.145
Health care barriers	Informed-connected	No barriers	0.110
Health care barriers	Informed-connected	Some barriers	0.517
Health care barriers	Informed-connected	Many barriers	0.372
Health care barriers	Moderate-mixed	No barriers	0.059
Health care barriers	Moderate-mixed	Some barriers	0.405
Health care barriers	Moderate-mixed	Many barriers	0.536
Health care barriers	Vulnerable-disconnected	No barriers	0.019
Health care barriers	Vulnerable-disconnected	Some barriers	0.201
Health care barriers	Vulnerable-disconnected	Many barriers	0.780
Health care utilisation	Informed-connected	No utilisation	0.395
Health care utilisation	Informed-connected	Utilisation	0.605
Health care utilisation	Moderate-mixed	No utilisation	0.606

Variable	Class	Category	Probability
Health care utilisation	Moderate-mixed	Utilisation	0.394
Health care utilisation	Vulnerable-disconnected	No Utilisation	0.600
Health care utilisation	Vulnerable-disconnected	utilisation	0.400
Education level	Informed-connected	No education	0.000
Education level	Informed-connected	Primary/Secondary	0.110
Education level	Informed-connected	Higher	0.890
Education level	Moderate-mixed	No education	0.060
Education level	Moderate-mixed	Primary/Secondary	0.695
Education level	Moderate-mixed	Higher	0.245
Education level	Vulnerable-disconnected	No education	0.549
Education level	Vulnerable-disconnected	Primary/Secondary	0.438
Education level	Vulnerable-disconnected	Higher	0.014

Class labels correspond to Figure S5 profiles: 'informed-connected' (high knowledge, high media, low barriers), 'moderate-mixed' (intermediate profiles), 'vulnerable-disconnected' (low knowledge, high barriers). TB: tuberculosis; LCA: Latent Class Analysis.

Table S14. Prevalence of self-reported health care access barriers among women of reproductive age ($n = 29,889$), Peru ENDES 2024.

Barrier	Variable	N Reported	% Reported
Not knowing where to go	v467a	4,381	14.7
Needing permission to go	v467b	3,509	11.7
Getting money for treatment	v467c	16,163	54.1
Distance to health facility	v467d	11,010	36.8
Getting transportation	v467e	10,802	36.1
Not wanting to go alone	v467f	10,516	35.2
No female health provider	v467g	12,266	41.0
No health provider available	v467h	25,294	84.6
No medications available	v467i	25,820	86.4

ENDES: Encuesta demográfica y de Salud Familiar (Peru Demographic and Health Survey).

Table S15. Multilevel logistic regression of comprehensive tuberculosis knowledge including perceived health care access barriers: adjusted odds ratios (Model M5).

Variable	OR	95% CI	P value
Age group			
15-24 (ref.)	1.00		
25-34	1.63	(1.51-1.76)	<0.001
35-44	2.28	(2.11-2.47)	<0.001
45-49	2.49	(2.23-2.78)	<0.001
Education level			
No education (ref.)	1.00		
Primary	1.64	(1.14-2.34)	0.007
Secondary	2.96	(2.07-4.22)	<0.001
Higher	4.34	(3.03-6.21)	<0.001
Media exposure			
No media (ref.)	1.00		
1 source	1.11	(0.94-1.30)	0.221
2-3 sources	1.13	(0.97-1.32)	0.105
Wealth index			
Poorest (ref.)	1.00		
Poorer	1.06	(0.96-1.17)	0.276

Variable	OR	95% CI	P value
Middle	1.08	(0.96-1.21)	0.22
Richer	1.19	(1.03-1.37)	0.019
Richest	1.15	(1.01-1.31)	0.03
Improved water source	1.12	(1.00-1.25)	0.045
Improved sanitation	1.02	(0.93-1.11)	0.737
Area of residence			
Urban (ref.)	1.00		
Rural	1.03	(0.94-1.14)	0.485
Altitude (scaled)	0.88	(0.85-0.92)	<0.001
Region			
Coast (ref.)	1.00		
Highlands	1.45	(1.15-1.83)	0.002
Jungle	1.43	(1.13-1.81)	0.003
Departmental TB incidence rate	1.13	(0.94-1.35)	0.189
Barriers category			
None (ref.)	1.00		
1-2 barriers	0.97	(0.86-1.10)	0.685
3-4 barriers	0.92	(0.82-1.04)	0.186
5+ barriers	0.82	(0.72-0.92)	<0.001

OR = odds ratio; CI = confidence interval; TB = tuberculosis

Table S16. Multilevel logistic regression of health care utilisation as a function of comprehensive tuberculosis knowledge and socio-demographic characteristics.

Variable	OR	95% CI	P value
Comprehensive TB knowledge	1.16	[1.09-1.23]	<0.001
Age group			
15-24 (ref.)	1.00		
25-34	1.31	[1.23-1.39]	<0.001
35-44	1.46	[1.37-1.57]	<0.001
45-49	1.61	[1.46-1.77]	<0.001
Education level			
No education (ref.)	1.00		
Primary	1.01	[0.8-1.28]	0.924
Secondary	1.19	[0.94-1.51]	0.157

Variable	OR	95% CI	P value
Higher	1.69	[1.33-2.16]	<0.001
Media exposure			
No media (ref.)	1.00		
1 source	1.15	[1.00-1.31]	0.044
2-3 sources	1.19	[1.05-1.35]	0.005
Wealth index			
Poorest (ref.)	1.00		
Poorer	0.99	[0.91-1.07]	0.728
Middle	1.04	[0.94-1.15]	0.41
Richer	1.63	[1.44-1.85]	<0.001
Richest	1.15	[1.03-1.28]	0.015
Area of residence			
Urban (ref.)	1.00		
Rural	1.28	[1.17-1.39]	<0.001
Region			
Coast (ref.)	1.00		
Highlands	1.02	[0.69-1.51]	0.919
Jungle	0.76	[0.47-1.24]	0.268

OR: odds ratio; CI: confidence interval; TB: tuberculosis.

Table S17. Multi-model selection for comprehensive tuberculosis knowledge: top candidate models ranked by Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC).

(Intercept)	Improved water source	Altitude (scaled)	Area of residence	Age group	Education level	Departmental TB incidence rate	Media exposure	Region	Improved sanitation	Health care service utilisation	df	Log Lik	BIC	delta	weight
-3.986	0.450			+	+	0.279		+		0.215	12	-4,427	8,964	0.000	0.203
-3.934	0.452			+	+	0.291		+			11	-4,433	8,968	3.705	0.032
-3.957	0.452	-0.038		+	+	0.274		+		0.213	13	-4,426	8,972	7.693	0.004
-3.708	0.418			+	+	0.199				0.223	10	-4,441	8,973	9.108	0.002
-3.988	0.430			+	+	0.276		+	0.043	0.214	13	-4,427	8,973	9.121	0.002
-3.959	0.444		+	+	+	0.275		+		0.216	13	-4,427	8,973	9.202	0.002
-4.249	0.438			+	+	0.282	+	+		0.214	14	-4,423	8,974	9.634	0.002
-3.903	0.454	-0.041		+	+	0.286		+			12	-4,432	8,975	11.044	0.001
-3.937	0.429			+	+	0.288		+	0.051		12	-4,433	8,977	12.764	<0.001
-3.915	0.447		+	+	+	0.289		+			12	-4,433	8,977	12.941	<0.001

TB: tuberculosis; BIC: Bayesian Information Criterion; df: degrees of freedom; Log Lik: log-likelihood.

Table S18. Relative importance of predictor variables from multi-model inference (model-averaged weights).

Variable	Importance
Age group	1.000
Education level	1.000
Departmental TB incidence rate	1.000
Improved water source	1.000
Region	0.990
Health care service utilisation	0.865
Altitude (scaled)	0.021
Improved sanitation	0.010
Area of residence	0.010
Media exposure	0.008
Wealth index	0.000

TB: tuberculosis.

Table S19. Mediation analysis: indirect effect of perceived health care access barriers on the association between socio-demographic characteristics and comprehensive tuberculosis knowledge.

Effect	Estimate	95% CI	<i>P</i> value
ACME (indirect effect)	-0.0002	[-0.0008, 0.0004]	0.472
ADE (direct effect)	0.0442	[0.0318, 0.0573]	<0.001
Total effect	0.0440	[0.0317, 0.0572]	<0.001
Proportion mediated	-0.0050	[-0.0200, 0.0090]	0.472

ACME: average causation mediation effect; ADE: average direct effect; CI: confidence interval.

Table S20. Random forest variable importance for predictors of comprehensive tuberculosis knowledge: mean decrease in accuracy and Gini index.

Variable	Mean Decrease Accuracy	Mean Decrease Gini
Altitude (scaled)	21.97	371.24
Age	13.56	287.34
Number of barriers	-1.91	137.78
Wealth index	15.95	94.52
Education level	32.41	84.43
Region	22.41	63.18
Media exposure	1.77	53.85
Health care service utilisation	-1.56	43.13
Improved sanitation	10.47	32.78
Area of residence	18.56	31.31
Improved water source	9.80	30.74
Health insurance	-0.33	25.23
Geographical barrier	0.00	0.00
Economic barrier	0.00	0.00

TB: tuberculosis.

Figures

Figure S1. Tuberculosis incidence rate by department, Peru, 2021. Choropleth map showing reported TB incidence per 100,000 population across Peru's 25 departments. Higher incidence is concentrated in the Jungle region (Ucayali, Loreto, Madre de Dios) and the metropolitan area (Lima, Callao). Data source: Ministerio de Salud (MINS), Peru, 2021. TB = tuberculosis.

Figure S2. Comprehensive tuberculosis knowledge by education level and wealth quintile. Weighted prevalence of comprehensive TB knowledge stratified by education (none, primary, secondary, higher) and household wealth index quintile (Q1 poorest to Q5 richest), showing a clear dose-response gradient for both determinants. Data source: Peru Demographic and Health Survey (ENDES) 2024 ($n = 29,889$). TB = tuberculosis.

Figure S3. Moran scatter plot: spatial autocorrelation of tuberculosis knowledge. Cluster-level weighted prevalence of comprehensive TB knowledge plotted against the spatial lag (mean of neighbouring clusters' prevalence). Global Moran's $I = 0.077$ ($P < 0.001$); $n = 3,074$ clusters; spatial weights: k -nearest neighbours ($k = 8$). Data source: Peru Demographic and Health Survey (ENDES) 2024. TB = tuberculosis.

Figure S4. Variable importance from random forest classification. Mean decrease in the Gini index for each predictor variable, ranked from most to least important. The random forest model was fitted using a 70/30 training-test split with 500 trees. Data source: Peru Demographic and Health Survey (ENDES) 2024 ($n = 29,889$). TB = tuberculosis.

Figure S5. Latent class profiles (three-class model). Conditional probabilities of 'high' category membership for each indicator variable across the three identified latent classes: 'informed-connected' (high knowledge, high media, low barriers), 'vulnerable-disconnected' (low knowledge, high barriers), and 'moderate-mixed' (intermediate profiles). Latent Class Analysis fitted using the poLCA package. Data source: Peru Demographic and Health Survey (ENDES) 2024. LCA = Latent Class Analysis; TB = tuberculosis.

Figure S6. Cluster-level tuberculosis (TB) knowledge in high-burden departments. Distribution of cluster-level weighted prevalence of comprehensive TB knowledge within departments classified as 'high-burden' (TB incidence ≥ 100 per 100,000 population). Data source: Peru Demographic and Health Survey (ENDES) 2024; TB incidence: MINSA 2021. TB = tuberculosis.

Figure S7. Distribution of perceived health care access barriers. Histogram of the total barrier score (range 0–9) across the study sample. The dashed line indicates the sample mean (4.01). Barriers were derived from nine binary items (v467a–i) addressing perceived difficulties in accessing health care. Data source: Peru Demographic and Health Survey (ENDES) 2024 ($n = 29,889$).

Figure S8. Relationship between tuberculosis (TB) knowledge and perceived access barriers at the cluster level. Cluster-level weighted prevalence of comprehensive TB knowledge plotted against the mean barrier score. Weighted $r = -0.18$, unweighted $r = -0.177$ ($P < 0.001$); $n = 3,074$ clusters. Data source: Peru Demographic and Health Survey (ENDES) 2024. TB = tuberculosis.

MEDIATION RESULTS
 Indirect (ACME): -0.0002 [-0.0008, 0.0004] (ns)
 Direct (ADE): 0.0442^{***}
 Proportion mediated: -0.5%

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$, ns = not significant

Figure S9. Mediation analysis: tuberculosis knowledge, perceived barriers, and health service utilisation. Path diagram showing the estimated causal mediation pathway from comprehensive TB knowledge through perceived health care access barriers to health service utilisation. Coefficients estimated using non-parametric bootstraps with 1,000 simulations. Data source: Peru Demographic and Health Survey (ENDES) 2024 ($n = 29,889$). ACME = average causal mediation effect; ADE = average direct effect; TB = tuberculosis.

Figure S10. Education × barriers interaction effect. Predicted probability of comprehensive tuberculosis knowledge by education level and perceived health care access barrier count, based on the fully adjusted multilevel logistic regression model (M4) with an added interaction term. Data source: Peru Demographic and Health Survey (ENDES) 2024 ($n = 29,889$). TB = tuberculosis.

Figure S11. Partial dependence plots for top predictors (random forest). Marginal effect of each predictor variable on the predicted probability of comprehensive tuberculosis knowledge, estimated from the random forest model. The four variables with the largest mean decrease in Gini index are displayed. Data source: Peru Demographic and Health Survey (ENDES) 2024 ($n = 29,889$). TB = tuberculosis.

Figure S12. Model diagnostics panel. Systematic verification of multilevel logistic regression assumptions for the fully adjusted model (M4): residual distribution, Q-Q plot of random effects at the cluster and department levels, linearity assessment via Generalised Additive Model smooth terms, and overdispersion test. Data source: Peru Demographic and Health Survey (ENDES) 2024 ($n = 29,889$; 3,074 clusters; 25 departments). GAM = Generalised Additive Model.